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Fundamentals of the Tax System

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Dotsent

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the basics of the tax system, which is a key element of public finance and economic regulation. It considers the types of taxes, including direct and indirect, as well as their classification by taxation levels. The main principles of taxation, such as fairness, simplicity, efficiency and progressivity, are discussed. Particular attention is paid to the functions of the tax system, including fiscal, regulatory, redistributive and incentive functions. It also considers the current problems faced by the tax system, such as high tax burden, tax evasion and complexity of legislation. In conclusion, the need to optimize the tax system is emphasized to achieve sustainable economic growth and improve the quality of life of citizens.

Keywords: Tax system, Direct taxes, Indirect taxes, Profit tax, Income tax, Value added tax (VAT), Excise taxes, National taxes, Local taxes
Виды налогов.

INTRODUCTION(KIRISH)

Taxes can be classified according to various criteria.

Direct taxes are mandatory payments that are levied directly on the income or property of taxpayers. They are determined based on the financial capabilities and status of the taxpayer, which makes them one of the main instruments for the

redistribution of income in society. Let's consider in more detail the main types of direct taxes, their functions and features

Types of direct taxes: Income tax. Income tax in Uzbekistan is levied on legal entities based on their profits. The tax rate is 15%. Features: There are benefits for certain categories of businesses, such as small businesses and enterprises in free economic zones.

Individual income tax (PIT) PIT in Uzbekistan applies to the income of individuals. The tax rates are progressive: 12% for income.

Property tax. Property tax is levied on individuals and legal entities for owning real estate. The rates depend on the type of property and its value.

4. Land tax. Land tax is levied on land owners. The rate is set depending on the category of land and its location.

5. Inheritance and Gift Tax

Inheritance and gift taxes are levied when property is transferred. Rates depend on the value of the property being transferred and the relationship between the parties.

Indirect taxes are mandatory payments that are not levied directly on the taxpayer's income, but are included in the cost of goods and services. These taxes are paid by end consumers upon purchase, not by the business itself. Indirect taxes are an important part of the tax system, providing significant revenues to the state budget. Let's consider in more detail the main types of indirect taxes, their functions and features

METHODOLOGY(METODOLOGIYA)

Types of indirect taxes. Value Added Tax (VAT)

VAT is a tax that is levied at each stage of production and sale of goods and services. It applies to all stages of the production chain. Rate: In Uzbekistan, the basic VAT rate is 12% and 0%.

Excise taxes. Excise taxes are special taxes levied on certain goods, such as alcohol, tobacco, petroleum products and cars. Excise rates can be fixed or percentage and vary depending on the type of goods. Customs duties. These are taxes levied on imported and exported goods. Fees can be either fixed or percentage.

Principles of Taxation. The principles of taxation form the basis of an effective and fair tax system. They help ensure sustainable financing of public needs, and also promote economic development and social justice.

Equity - The tax system must be fair, which means equal taxation of persons with equal financial opportunities and different rates for persons with different incomes.

Transparency - The tax system should be clear and accessible to taxpayers. Taxpayers should be able to easily understand how taxes are calculated and what rules apply.

Simplicity - The process of paying taxes and complying with tax obligations should be simple and convenient for citizens and businesses. Complex tax systems can lead to errors and reduced compliance.

Efficiency - The tax system should provide sufficient revenue to the budget with minimal administrative costs. This means that the cost of collecting taxes should be as low as possible.

Progressivity - Taxes should be progressive, that is, higher incomes should be taxed at higher rates. This contributes to the redistribution of income and the reduction of social inequality.

Predictability - The tax system should be stable so that taxpayers can plan their financial expenses and investments. Frequent changes in tax laws can lead to uncertainty and risks

Function of the Tax System. The tax system performs several key functions that ensure its effective functioning and impact on the economy and society.

Fiscal function. The main function of the tax system is to raise funds to finance government spending. Taxes provide the revenue needed to perform government functions such as health care, education, defense, and social security.

Regulatory function - Taxes can be used to regulate economic activity, influencing the behavior of citizens and businesses. With the help of tax policy, the state can stimulate or restrict certain types of activity.

Redistributive function - Taxes help redistribute income in society, reducing social inequality. This is achieved through progressive taxation and social programs.

Stimulating function - The tax system can encourage certain economic activities, such as investment in certain sectors or social initiatives.

Control function - The tax system serves as a tool for monitoring economic activity, income and expenses of citizens and businesses. Taxes help identify the informal economy and tax evasion.

Social function - Taxes help finance social programs and services, such as health care, education and pensions, which helps improve the quality of life of citizens.

Information function - The tax system provides information on the state of the economy, the level of income and expenses of the population, which helps the state in making economic decisions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION(NATIJAR VA MUHOKAMA)

Problems of the tax system. The tax system of each country faces various problems that can negatively affect its efficiency and fairness. Let's look at the main problems of the tax system:

1. **High tax burden** - In conditions of high tax burden, businesses and citizens have difficulties paying taxes, which can lead to tax evasion and a decrease in investment activity.

2. **Tax evasion** - A significant number of taxpayers evade taxes, which leads to a shortfall in budget revenues.

3. **Complexity of tax legislation** - Frequent changes and complexity of tax legislation can create confusion and make it difficult to comply with tax obligations.

4. **Insufficient transparency** - Non-transparent tax mechanisms and a lack of information on tax policy can cause mistrust on the part of taxpayers.

5. Inefficient administration - Tax authorities may face a lack of resources, insufficient qualifications of employees and outdated technologies..

6. Regressiveness of Taxation - Some taxes, such as indirect taxes, can be regressive, meaning that they place a higher burden on low-income people.

Conclusion. The tax system plays a key role in the functioning of the state by providing financial resources to carry out its functions and services. Effective taxation contributes to economic growth, social justice and sustainable development. However, the tax system faces a number of problems, such as high tax burden, tax evasion, complexity of legislation and lack of transparency. To improve the efficiency of the tax system, it is necessary to carry out reforms aimed at simplifying tax legislation, improving administration and ensuring a fair distribution of the tax burden. It is also important to work on increasing the level of trust in tax authorities and combating corruption. Addressing these issues will help create a fairer, more transparent and efficient tax system that promotes sustainable economic development and improves the quality of life of citizens. Thus, tax policy should not only collect revenue for the state, but also contribute to the harmonious development of society as a whole.

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